

Appendix A and B, and the Supplementary Data

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Appendix A: Eight Factor Model for Agency

Table A.1

Standardised Loadings from the Eight Factor Model for Agency

	Competence beliefs	Self-efficacy	Trust for teacher	Teacher support	Participation activity	Ease of participation	Opportunities to influence	Interest and utility value
Sufficient basis for participation in discussions in the course	0.726							
Experiencing course contents as too challenging*	0.777							
Lacking basic knowledge for understanding the course contents*	0.737							
Experience of need for revision of basic concepts prior to the course*	0.776							
Course demands have not been excessive	0.785							
Belief in succeeding even in the most challenging tasks		0.709						
Belief in successfully completing the course		0.826						
Confidence in oneself as a learner despite of challenges		0.797						
Belief in one's ability to succeed in the course		0.879						
Belief in attaining personal goals set for the course		0.787						
Possibility to be oneself in the course			0.554					
Experience of being able to trust teachers			0.687					

Experience of being welcome in the course	0.726	
Approachability of the teachers	0.789	
Safe course climate	0.728	
Belittling of students by teachers*	0.835	
Not enough room for discussion given by teachers*	0.556	
Teachers' contemptuous attitude towards students*	0.869	
Expressing opinions on the course		0.799
Enjoyment in taking initiatives and collaborating in the course		0.560
Taking responsibility by being an active participant		0.646
Possibility to express thoughts and views without being ridiculed		0.580
Difficulties participating in discussions*		0.632
Courage to challenge matters presented in the course		0.486
Ease of participation in discussions		0.733
Experience of having to perform according to external instructions*		0.606
No possibility to influence the course contents*		0.377
No opportunities to influence the goals set for this course*		0.333
Opportunity to influence how competence is assessed in the course		0.320
High motivation to study in the course		0.770
The course was not inspiring because of unclear utility value*		0.589
Desire to learn in order to understand		0.512

Note. The AUS Scale is copyrighted, its use requires written permission from the main developer; contact information: paivikki.jaaskela@jyu.fi For this study, the written permission has been granted by the scale developers. * Reversed-coded item.

Table A.2*Correlations of Dimensions of Agency*

Resource Domain	Dimension of agency	CB	SE	TT	TS	PA	EP	OI	IU
Personal resources	Competence beliefs (CB)	1	.81***	.32***	.35***	.03	.36***	.59***	.44***
	Self-efficacy (SE)		1	.46***	.27***	.31***	.50***	.46***	.69***
Relational resources	Trust for teacher (TT)			1	.72***	.19*	.78***	.53***	.61***
	Teacher support (TS)				1	-.09	.43***	.50***	.46***
Participatory resources	Participation activity (PA)					1	.64***	.29*	.45***
	Ease of participation (EP)						1	.59***	.54***
	Opportunities to influence (OI)							1	.42***
	Interest and utility value (IU)								1

Note. Correlation coefficients between dimensions of agency from CFA ($N = 309$). CB = Competence beliefs, SE = Self-efficacy, TT = Trust for teacher, TS = Teacher support, PA = Participation activity, EP = Ease of participation, OI = Opportunities to influence, IU = Interest and utility value. * $p \leq .05$, ** $p \leq .01$, *** $p \leq .001$.

Table A.3*Correlations of the Agency Resource Domains*

Resource domain	PeR	ReR	PaR
Personal resources (PeR)	1		
Relational resources (ReR)	.39***	1	
Participatory resources (PaR)	.67***	.77***	1

Note. Correlation coefficients between second order agency factors from CFA ($N = 309$).

*** $p < .001$

Table A.4*Reliabilities of the Dimensions of Agency*

Dimension of Agency	McDonald's Omega (ω)	<i>p</i>-value
Competence beliefs	.887	<.001
Self-efficacy	.904	<.001
Trust for teacher	.835	<.001
Teacher support	.698	<.001
Participation activity	.678	<.001
Ease of participation	.704	<.001
Opportunities to influence	.562	<.001
Interest and utility value	.647	<.001

Table A.5*Main Effects of Background Characteristics for Each Dimension of Agency*

Resource domain	Dimension of Agency	Field of Study				<i>F</i> (1,260)	<i>p</i>	η_p^2
		M	SD	M	SD			
		Tec. <i>n</i> = 195		Bus. <i>n</i> = 67				
Personal resources	Competence beliefs	3.4	0.8	3.7	0.8	2.3	.134	.009
	Self-efficacy	3.8	0.9	3.8	0.8	0.0	.987	.000
Relational resources	Trust for teacher	4.4	0.6	3.9	0.7	27.2	<.001	.096
	Teacher support	4.5	0.6	4.2	0.9	8.3	.004	.031
Participatory resources	Participation activity	3.0	0.8	2.8	0.9	2.5	.112	.010
	Ease of participation	3.8	0.6	3.4	0.7	16.5	<.001	.060
	Opportunities to influence	3.3	0.6	3.1	0.7	3.7	.056	.014
	Interest and utility value	4.2	0.6	4.0	0.5	7.0	.008	.027

Resource domain	Dimension of Agency	M	SD	M	SD	<i>F</i> (1,260)	<i>p</i>	η_p^2
Gender								
		W <i>n</i> = 54		M <i>n</i> = 208				
Personal resources	Competence beliefs	3.6	0.9	3.5	0.8	0.0	.966	.000
	Self-efficacy	3.7	1.0	3.8	0.8	0.2	.966	.000
Relational resources	Trust for teacher	4.2	0.7	4.3	0.6	0.5	.502	.002
	Teacher support	4.4	0.8	4.4	0.7	0.9	.333	.004
Participatory resources	Participation activity	2.9	0.8	2.9	0.8	0.1	.795	.000
	Ease of participation	3.6	0.7	3.7	0.7	0.2	.693	.001
	Opportunities to influence	3.3	0.7	3.3	0.6	0.3	.585	.001
	Interest and utility value	4.1	0.6	4.1	0.5	1.4	.235	.005
Age								
		18–21 y <i>n</i> = 129		22 y or more <i>n</i> = 133				
Personal resources	Competence beliefs	3.6	0.7	3.4	0.9	5.2	.024	.020
	Self-efficacy	3.8	0.8	3.7	0.9	1.3	.255	.005
Relational resources	Trust for teacher	4.2	0.6	4.3	0.6	0.2	.663	.001
	Teacher support	4.4	0.7	4.4	0.7	0.0	.893	.000
Participatory resources	Participation activity	3.0	0.7	2.9	0.8	0.3	.560	.001
	Ease of participation	3.7	0.6	3.7	0.7	0.3	.577	.001
	Opportunities to influence	3.3	0.6	3.2	0.6	4.9	.028	.019
	Interest and utility value	4.1	0.5	4.1	0.6	0.1	.705	.001
Study credits								
		No credits (0 ects) <i>n</i> = 164		Credits (1 or more ects) <i>n</i> = 98				
Personal resources	Competence beliefs	3.5	0.8	3.5	0.9	0.1	.734	.000
	Self-efficacy	3.8	0.8	3.7	1.0	0.7	.406	.003
		4.3	0.6	4.3	0.7	0.7	.394	.003

Resource domain	Dimension of Agency	M	SD	M	SD	<i>F</i> (1,260)	<i>p</i>	η_p^2
Relational resources	Trust for teacher	4.4	0.7	4.4	0.7	0.0	.955	.000
	Teacher support	4.4	0.7	4.4	0.7	0.0	.955	.000
Participatory resources	Participation activity	3.0	0.7	2.8	0.9	1.2	.277	.005
	Ease of participation	3.7	0.6	3.6	0.7	0.6	.458	.002
	Opportunities to influence	3.3	0.6	3.2	0.7	0.5	.495	.002
	Interest and utility value	4.2	0.5	4.1	0.6	2.0	.156	.008

Note. Estimates from ANOVA main effects model for dimensions of agency ($N = 262$), Tec. = Technology, Bus. = Business management, W = women, M = men, $F(1,260)$ = ANOVA test statistic ($df1, df2$), $p = p$ -value from F -test for each main effect, η_p^2 = partial eta squared.

Table A.6

Interaction Effects Between Background Characteristics for Each Dimension of Agency

Dimension of agency	M		SD		M		SD		<i>F</i> (1, 260)	<i>p</i>	η_p^2
	Field * Gender										
	Tec.				Bus.						
W <i>n</i> = 24		M <i>n</i> = 171		W <i>n</i> = 30		M <i>n</i> = 37					
Competence beliefs	3.75 ^{ab}	0.82	3.40 ^b	0.81	3.41 ^{ab}	0.88	3.87 ^a	0.69	9.23	.003	.035
Self-efficacy	4.01 ^{ab}	0.79	3.72 ^{ab}	0.87	3.44 ^b	1.00	4.02 ^a	0.60	8.99	.003	.034
Trust for teacher	4.53	0.46	4.37	0.59	3.89	0.76	3.97	0.56	1.30	.255	.005
Teacher support	4.60	0.61	4.45	0.63	4.23	0.95	4.17	0.79	0.13	.718	.001
Participation activity	2.97	0.77	2.98	0.76	2.81	0.84	2.81	0.89	0.00	.973	.000
Ease of participation	3.91	0.55	3.77	0.64	3.34	0.66	3.47	0.68	1.25	.264	.005

Dimension of agency	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	<i>F</i> (1, 260)	<i>p</i>	η_p^2
Opportunities to influence	3.50	0.61	3.26	0.64	3.07	0.69	3.22	0.67	3.24	.073	.013
Interest and utility value	4.34	0.52	4.15	0.58	3.96	0.61	4.01	0.37	2.76	.098	.011

Study credits * Gender

	No credits (0 ects)				Credits (1 or more ects)				<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>	η_p^2
	W <i>n</i> = 25		M <i>n</i> = 139		W <i>n</i> = 29		M <i>n</i> = 69				
Competence beliefs	3.68	0.61	3.50	0.78	3.46	1.04	3.46	0.86	0.28	.597	.001
Self-efficacy	3.79	0.76	3.83	0.76	3.61	1.09	3.67	0.97	0.02	.902	.000
Trust for teacher	4.33	0.56	4.28	0.61	4.04	0.81	4.34	0.60	1.45	.230	.006
Teacher support	4.57 ^a	0.52	4.35 ^a	0.70	4.24 ^a	1.02	4.49 ^a	0.57	4.18	.042	.016
Participation activity	2.89	0.80	3.01	0.72	2.88	0.83	2.83	0.90	1.80	.181	.007
Ease of participation	3.71	0.61	3.72	0.63	3.50	0.72	3.71	0.71	0.02	.902	.000
Opportunities to influence	3.43	0.54	3.23	0.65	3.11	0.77	3.31	0.63	1.57	.212	.006
Interest and utility value	4.20	0.54	4.15	0.51	4.06	0.64	4.08	0.62	0.02	.876	.000

Field * Age

	Tec.				Bus.				<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>	η_p^2
	18–21 y		22 y or more		18–21 y		22 y or more				
Competence beliefs	3.58	0.81	3.34	0.81	3.75	0.57	3.53	1.07	0.49	.483	.002
Self-efficacy	3.82	0.85	3.70	0.88	3.90	0.57	3.55	1.13	0.50	.479	.002
Trust for teacher	4.36	0.62	4.42	0.55	3.99	0.53	3.85	0.80	0.49	.483	.002
Teacher support	4.47	0.63	4.46	0.62	4.15	0.85	4.27	0.90	2.32	.129	.009
Participation activity	2.97 ^{ab}	0.73	2.98 ^a	0.79	3.01 ^{ab}	0.80	2.52 ^b	0.89	5.36	.021	.021
Ease of participation	3.78	0.67	3.79	0.60	3.55	0.57	3.21	0.76	1.97	.162	.008
Opportunities to influence	3.37	0.67	3.23	0.60	3.25	0.60	3.00	0.77	0.08	.780	.000
Interest and utility value	4.16	0.58	4.19	0.57	4.04	0.40	3.91	0.59	0.76	.383	.003

Note. Estimates are from ANOVA interaction effects model for dimensions of agency (*N* = 262). Significant interactions are from the final model with the main effects and only

significant interactions, and nonsignificant interactions are from the model with all two-way interactions. For significant interactions, significance of differences between groups are labelled with superscripts (different superscripts indicate $p \leq .05$). Tec. = Technology, Bus. = Business management, W = women, M = men, $F(1,260)$ = ANOVA test statistic ($df1$, $df2$), p = p -value from F -test for each main effect, η_p^2 = partial eta squared.

Appendix B: Temporal Variation of Agency

Based on repeated quantitative measurements, the power analysis indicated that $N = 16$ was adequate to observe a difference of 0.4 points in dimensions of agency between time points as significant within data for one participant. The eight-factor model for agency was utilised by extracting the factor score coefficients from Study 1 data with Mplus Version 8.10 (Muthén & Muthén 1998–2017) and used to compute the scaled factor scores for each time point in Study 2 with R 4.2.1 (R Core Team, 2022). Pairwise mean differences of the agency dimensions factor scores between time points were computed for each participant, and significances of the differences were estimated comparing the difference to a cut-off value for statistically significant absolute difference, both computed separately for each agency factor. These cut-off values correspond to two times the standard deviation of the estimated measurement error calculated with Cronbach's alpha, computed with IBM SPSS Statistics 28.0.0.1. To reject the possibility that the change was due to measurement error, the probability threshold was set to .05.

Table B.1

Individual Differences Between Timepoints for Dimensions of Agency

Dimension of agency	CB	SE	TT	TS	PA	EP	OI	IU	
<i>Cut-off for significant absolute difference*</i>	0.40	0.39	0.33	0.35	0.53	0.55	0.46	0.36	
$t_2 - t_1$ ($n = 11$)									
ID	1								
	2	-0.16	-0.11	-0.04	-0.43	-0.05	-0.34	0.04	0.06
	3								
	4	1.44	1.56	1.96	1.91	0.37	1.50	2.05	1.76
	5	0.38	0.06	0.21	0.18	0.38	0.13	0.92	0.71
	6	0.12	-0.51	-0.36	-0.44	-1.05	-0.63	0.18	-0.80
	7	0.89	0.06	0.37	0.41	-0.66	0.09	0.63	-0.26
	8								
	9	0.00	-0.11	0.05	0.00	-0.40	-0.10	-0.11	-0.03
	10	1.31	0.35	-0.04	-0.20	-0.69	-0.55	0.50	0.04
	11								
	12	1.03	0.54	0.31	0.28	-1.12	-0.42	0.48	0.56
	13	-0.20	-0.46	-0.23	-0.05	-0.72	-0.77	0.21	0.02
	14	0.01	-0.03	-0.04	-0.33	0.08	0.02	-0.04	-0.62
	15	1.41	0.41	0.09	0.09	-0.64	-0.07	0.96	-0.08
	16								
$t_3 - t_1$ ($n = 11$)									
	1	-1.79	-1.53	0.00	-0.08	-1.25	0.62	-0.62	-1.65
	2								
	3	-1.93	-1.28	-1.25	-0.37	-2.65	-2.40	-1.77	-0.21
	4	0.73	0.48	1.09	1.73	-1.78	0.26	0.49	0.89

Dimension of agency	CB	SE	TT	TS	PA	EP	OI	IU		
<i>Cut-off for significant absolute difference*</i>	0.40	0.39	0.33	0.35	0.53	0.55	0.46	0.36		
ID	5	0.30	-0.34	-0.17	0.04	0.73	0.55	0.47	0.29	
	6									
	7									
	8	0.37	0.34	0.02	-0.08	0.39	0.32	0.42	0.02	
	9	-0.20	-0.67	0.04	0.00	0.31	0.95	-0.62	-0.16	
	10	0.07	-1.10	-1.28	-1.07	-1.02	-1.55	0.00	-1.35	
	11	1.61	0.59	0.85	0.56	1.13	1.71	1.35	0.61	
	12									
	13	0.00	-0.20	-0.49	-0.50	0.70	-0.15	0.38	0.29	
	14	0.53	0.43	-0.31	-1.12	0.93	0.65	0.02	-0.13	
	15	2.00	0.67	-0.16	0.07	-0.03	0.44	0.50	0.25	
	16									
	$t_3 - t_2$ ($n = 8$)									
	ID	1								
		2								
		3								
4		-0.72	-1.08	-0.87	-0.18	-2.15	-1.24	-1.56	-0.87	
5		-0.07	-0.40	-0.38	-0.13	0.35	0.42	-0.45	-0.42	
6										
7										
8										
9		-0.20	-0.56	0.00	0.00	0.71	1.05	-0.51	-0.13	
10		-1.24	-1.45	-1.24	-0.87	-0.33	-1.00	-0.50	-1.38	
11										
12										
13		0.20	0.26	-0.25	-0.45	1.43	0.63	0.18	0.27	
14		0.52	0.45	-0.27	-0.79	0.85	0.63	0.06	0.49	
15		0.59	0.26	-0.26	-0.02	0.61	0.52	-0.46	0.33	
16		-0.03	0.42	-0.45	-1.33	2.21	1.04	-0.30	0.38	

Note. Differences between time points in dimensions for agency for each participant (total $N = 16$). t_1, t_2, t_3 = Time points 1, 2 and 3, CB = Competence beliefs, SE = Self-efficacy, TT = Trust for teacher, TS = Teacher support, PA = Participation activity, EP = Ease of participation, OI = Opportunities to influence, IU = Interest and utility value.

* Cut-off value for significant absolute difference based on measurement error.

Supplementary Data

Tests of Measurement Invariance and Method Factor

Originally, eleven continuous latent factors could be identified in three domains of agency: personal resources (competence beliefs, self-efficacy); relational resources (equal treatment, trust for teacher, teacher support); and participatory resources of agency (participation activity, ease of participation, opportunities to influence, opportunities to make choices, interest and utility value, peer support) (Jääskelä et al., 2020).

The original 11-factor model fit moderately the Study 1 data (RMSEA = .058, SRMR = .078). To investigate to what extent the factorial invariance of the AUS scale with an 11-factor structure holds in the present data collected in the UAS context, invariance testing was performed with validated reference data from a research university ($N = 270$) (see Jääskelä et al., 2020). Evidence of full or partial scalar measurement invariance, suggesting a similar interpretation of the factor means, was found for eight factors and 32 items.

Measurement invariance tests evaluate the comparability of the data sets, which is done to validate the same construct having the same meaning and interpretation on the same metric (Putnick & Bornstein, 2016). Consecutive invariance testing (e.g., Meredith, 1993) was performed using multigroup CFA in Mplus Version 8.10 for UAS (University of Applied Sciences) data. Testing was performed separately for each factor to identify noninvariant items effectively because the entire 11-factor model did not identify distinctions between factors (Shi et al., 2019). The analysis was performed as described in detail in Jääskelä et al. (2023), with the same reference data from UNI (University of Jyväskylä). Reference data were collected from the master's degree programmes of different fields such as economics, psychology, and humanities, with 62% being women and a mean age of 23 years.

Invariance testing consisted of steps for configural invariance (no constraints), metric invariance (constraining loadings same across data) and scalar invariance (constraining additionally factor loadings and intercepts of items equal between data). In addition, residual invariance was tested. Scaled chi-square difference test (Satorra, 2000) and a change in RMSEA were used to test the equality of measurement structure (Beauducel & Wittman, 2005). If 50% of the items or at least three items in total were invariant, the factor could be incorporated into the model as partially invariant (e.g., Putnick & Bornstein, 2016). From 11 factors, scalar noninvariance was detected for factors peer support, opportunities to make choices and equal treatment; these were excluded from the following analyses (see Table S.1–S.11 below). Self-efficacy and Ease of participation had full scalar invariance, and the other six factors were partially invariant. Dimension Opportunities to influence had the three lowest loadings from all item loadings, but all four items were invariant and were kept in the following analyses. Therefore, evidence of full or partial scalar measurement invariance, here suggesting similar interpretation of the factor means using only invariant items, was found for eight factors.

Therefore, eight factors were utilized for this study. The final eight-factor model fit the data well (RMSEA = .053, SRMR = .065, CFI = .91, TLI = .89), and they were considered representing the meaning of original eight dimensions well. All standardised item loadings

were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) and ranged from .32 to .88, with most standardised loadings being above .60. Significant correlations between the dimensions ranged from .19 to .81 ($p < 0.05$), with only two bivariate correlations being nonsignificant (Appendix A). Additionally, the second-order factor model with three resource domains (personal, participatory, and relational) had a moderate fit (RMSEA = .062, SRMR = .078, CFI = .87, TLI = .85). All loadings of second-order factors were statistically significant ($p < .001$) (results not presented). Correlations between second-order factors ranged from .39 to .77 ($p < .001$) (Appendix A). However, second-order factors or domains of agency resources were only utilized as descriptive constructs and not utilised in presenting the results because the eight first-order factors were perceived as theoretically more informative for describing the multidimensional nature of agency.

Finally, when examining the associations between the agency dimensions and background characteristics, the number of participants was too small for multigroup CFA; therefore, the categories were assumed to be invariant.

Fitted Models

M1: Theoretical model without restrictions (Configural invariance)

M1mod: modified M1 (adding residual correlations)

M2: Testing equality of factor loadings (Metric invariance)

M2mod: Modified M2 (some or all loadings not restricted between organisations)

M3: Equality of intercepts. (Scalar invariance) Note. If loading of the item is estimated as unequal in organisations, the intercept is also estimated unequal.

M3mod: modified M3 (one or more intercepts estimated unequal between organisations)

M4: Testing equality of residual variances (Residual invariance)

M4mod: Modified M4 (one or more residual variances estimated unequal between organisations)

Table S.1*Measurement Invariance Tests of Competence Beliefs Factor (7 items)*

Model	χ^2	df	p	SC	RMSEA	CFI	TLI	SRMR	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δdf	p
M1 ^a	48.865	24	.002	1.2550	.060	.983	.969	.028	NA	NA	NA
M1mod ^b	33.996	22	.049	1.2477	.043	.991	.984	.025	14.16	2	<.001
M2	58.085	28	<.001	1.2129	.061	.979	.968	.086	25.83	6	<.001
M2mod ^c	51.029	27	.004	1,2167	.055	.983	.973	.076	18.21	5	.003
M2mod ^d	39.121	26	.048	1,2214	.042	.991	.985	.040	4.98	4	.289
M3	44.971	30	.039	1.1912	.042	.989	.985	.046	5.82	4	.213
M4	93.922	37	<.001	1.2131	.073	.959	.954	.080	44.97	7	<.001
M4mod ^e	50.686	36	.053	1.2235	.038	.990	.988	.043	6.10	6	.412

Note. UAS factor mean (Cohen's $d = 0.95$ relative to mean of standard deviations) is smaller than UNI mean ($p < .001$), and UAS factor variance is 1.99 times larger than UNI factor variance ($p < .001$).

^a Two residual correlations according of earlier theoretical model AUS10 WITH AUS5 and AUS49 WITH AUS30

^b Added one residual correlation according to large MI AUS15 WITH AUS30

^c Free loading AUS30; ^d free AUS49

^e Residual variance freely estimated AUS30

Table S.2*Measurement Invariance Tests of Self-efficacy (5 items)*

Model	χ^2	df	p	SC	RMSEA	CFI	TLI	SRMR	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δdf	p
M1 ^a	10.839	8	.211	1.2101	.035	.997	.993	.012	NA	NA	NA
M2	19.576	12	.076	1.2250	.047	.993	.988	.063	8.66	4	.070
M3	27.622	16	.035	1.1599	.050	.989	.986	.064	8.35	4	.079
M4	31.093	21	.072	1.2767	.041	.991	.991	.067	4.64	5	.461

Note. UAS factor mean (Cohen's $d = 0.47$ relative to mean of standard deviations) is smaller than UNI mean ($p < .001$), and UAS factor variance is 1.70 times larger than UNI variance ($p = .002$).

^a According to earlier theoretical model AUS59 WITH AUS55

Table S.3*Measurement Invariance Tests of Teacher Support (5 items)*

Model	χ^2	df	p	SC	RMSEA	CFI	TLI	SRMR	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δdf	p
M1	10.230	10	.421	1.7210	.009	.999	.999	.020	NA	NA	NA
M2	21.200	14	.094	1.7152	.042	.980	.971	.074	11.03	4	.026
M2mod ^a	14.302	13	.353	1.7241	.019	.996	.994	.049	4.07	3	.254
M3	23.452	16	.102	1.5446	.040	.979	.974	.063	15.08	3	.002
M3mod ^b	17.704	15	.279	1.6060	.025	.992	.990	.046	4.50	2	.105
M4	43.619	20	.002	2.0502	.064	.934	.934	.285	18.03	5	.003
M4mod ^c	15.721	18	.612	1.9700	.000	1.0	1.0	.050	0.67	3	.880

Note. UAS factor mean (Cohen's $d = 0.50$) relative to mean of standard deviations) is larger than UNI mean ($p = .031$), and UAS factor variance is 2.71 times larger than UNI variance ($p = .002$).

^a AUS20

^b AUS4

^c AUS4 and AUS11

Table S.4*Measurement Invariance Tests of Equal Treatment (3 items)*

Model	χ^2	df	p	SC	RMSEA	CFI	TLI	SRMR	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δdf	p
M1	saturated										
M2	2.852	2	.240	1.1990	.038	.995	.985	.044	2.852	2	.240
M3	11.074	4	.026	1.0664	.078	.958	.936	.063	8.98	2	.011
M4	4.052	5	.542	1.8399	.000	1.0	1.0	.069	1.78	3	.619

Note. Mean of item AUS32 in UNI ($M = 1.98$) is larger than UAS mean ($M = 0.74$) ($p = .003$), and UAS factor variance does not differ from UNI factor variance.

Table S.5*Measurement Invariance Tests of Trust for Teacher (7 items)*

Model	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	SC	RMSEA	CFI	TLI	SRMR	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δdf	<i>p</i>
M1 ^a	55.579	22	<.001	1.2045	.073	.965	.934	.030	-	-	-
M1mod ^b	13.230	16	.656	1.1967	.0	1.0	1.0	.015	41.71	6	<.001
M2	33.253	22	.058	1.2134	.042	.988	.978	.093	19.49	6	.003
M2mod ^c	20.925	21	.464	1.2179	.0	1.0	1.0	.060	7.51	5	.186
M3	114.696	26	<.001	1.1711	.109	.909	.852	.090	111.68	5	<.001
M3mod ^d	26.472	25	.383	1.1867	.014	.998	.997	.069	5.80	4	.215
M4	44.546	32	.069	1.5193	.037	.987	.983	.127	13.40	7	.063
M4mod ^e	25.691	31	.736	1.5137	0	1.0	1.0	.068	3.12	6	.793

Note. UAS factor mean is equal to UNI mean, and UAS factor variance does not differ from UNI variance.

^a AUS58 WITH AUS31, AUS23 WITH AUS24, AUS28 WITH AUS24

^b AUS31 WITH AUS56, AUS31 WITH AUS23, AUS28 WITH AUS23

^c AUS31

^d AUS58

^e AUS58

Table S.6*Measurement Invariance Tests of Interest and Utility Value (7 items)*

Model	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	SC	RMSEA	CFI	TLI	SRMR	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δdf	<i>p</i>
M1 ^a	74.090	24	<.001	1.1502	.085	.959	.928	.037	-	-	-
M1mod ^b	24.147	18	.150	1.1949	.034	.995	.988	.024	55.47	6	<.001
M2	44.417	24	.007	1.2127	.054	.983	.971	.072	19.75	6	.003
M2mod ^c	28.903	22	.148	1.2186	.033	.994	.989	.036	4.81	4	.308
M3	53.994	26	.001	1.1954	.061	.977	.963	.049	27.46	4	<.001
M3mod ^d	32.472	24	.116	1.2040	.035	.993	.988	.038	3.71	2	.156
M4	49.186	31	.020	1.2746	.045	.985	.980	.115	15.56	7	.029
M4mod ^e	39.272	30	.120	1.2631	.033	.992	.989	.065	7.01	6	.320

Note. UAS factor mean (Cohen's $d = 0.36$ relative to mean of standard deviations) is smaller than UNI mean, and UAS factor variance is 0.65 times smaller than UNI variance ($p < .001$).

^a According to earlier theory AUS13 WITH AUS47 and AUS52 WITH AUS13

^b AUS52 WITH AUS1, AUS50 WITH AUS13, AUS34 WITH AUS1

^c AUS52, AUS2

^d AUS47, AUS13

^e AUS13

Table S.7*Measurement Invariance Tests of Opportunities to Make Choices (3 items)*

Model	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	SC	RMSEA	CFI	TLI	SRMR	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δdf	<i>p</i>
M1	Saturated										
M2	3.112	2	.211	1.1096	.044	.993	.978	.028	NA	NA	NA
M3	25.836	4	<.001	0.9869	.137	.854	.781	.052	25.51	2	<.001
M4	16.938	5	.005	.9963	.091	.920	.904	.101	14.58	3	.002

Note. Mean of AUS29 in UNI ($M = 3.23$) is larger than UAS mean ($M = 2.95$) ($p = .004$), mean of AUS43 in UNI (2.96) is larger than UAS mean ($M = 2.71$) ($p = .008$), and UAS factor variance does not differ from UNI factor variance.

Table S.8*Measurement Invariance Tests of Participation Activity (5 items)*

Model	χ^2	df	p	SC	RMSEA	CFI	TLI	SRMR	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δdf	p
M1 ^a	6.115	6	.410	1.1437	.008	1.0	1.0	.015	NA	NA	NA
M2	12.956	10	.226	1.0830	.032	.997	.994	.041	6.84	4	.144
M3	66.915	14	<.001	1.0369	.114	.947	.924	.057	60.19	4	<.001
M3mod ^b	14.569	12	.266	1.0629	.027	.997	.996	.040	1.51	2	.471
M4	29.843	17	.028	1.0353	.051	.987	.985	.050	15.90	5	.007
M4mod ^c	17.753	16	.339	1.0380	.019	.998	.998	.053	3.05	4	.549

Note. UAS factor mean (Cohen's $d = 0.57$ relative to mean of standard deviations) is smaller than UNI mean, and UAS factor variance is 0.62 times smaller than UNI variance ($p < .001$).

^a According to earlier theory AUS12 and AUS6 AUS26

^b AUS6, AUS40

^c AUS53

Table S.9*Measurement Invariance Tests of Peer Support (5 items)*

Model	χ^2	df	p	SC	RMSEA	CFI	TLI	SRMR	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δdf	p
M1	6.632	6	.356	1.1634	.019	.998	.994	.017	NA	NA	NA
M2	8.269	10	.603	1.1657	0	1.0	1.0	.024	1.637	4	.802
M3	47.293	14	<.001	1.1537	.091	.906	.866	.074	39.98	4	<.001
M3mod ^a	NA										
M4	37.027	15	.001	1.1517	.071	.938	.917	.080	29.37	5	<.001
M4mod ^b	13.091	13	.441	1.1268	.005	1.0	1.0	.050	5.13	3	.997

Note. Means of items in UNI data AUS48 ($M = 3.58$), AUS42 ($M = 3.19$), AUS57 ($M = 3.93$) and AUS21 ($M = 1.77$) are lower than UAS means AUS48 ($M = 4.04$, $p < .001$), AUS42 ($M = 3.71$, $p < .001$), AUS57 ($M = 4.05$, $p = .001$) and AUS21 ($M = 1.97$, $p = .012$), and factor variance in UAS does not differ from factor variance in UNI.

^a AUS54, AUS21, AUS57

^b AUS57, AUS48

Table S.10*Measurement Invariance Tests of Opportunities to Influence (7 items)*

Model	χ^2	df	p	SC	RMSEA	CFI	TLI	SRMR	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δdf	p
M1 ^a	31.752	20	.046	1.0115	.045	.984	.967	.032	NA	NA	NA
M2	38.821	26	.051	1.0457	.041	.983	.972	.042	7.31	6	.293
M3	108.172	32	<.001	1.0105	.091	.897	.685	.070	80.09	6	<.001
M3mod ^b	43.785	29	.039	1.0411	.042	.980	.971	.043	4.98	3	.173
M4	54.317	36	.026	1.0273	.042	.975	.971	.076	10.53	7	.160
M4mod ^c	47.192	35	1.0259	1.0259	.035	.984	.980	.053	2.97	6	.812

Note. Factor mean of UAS does not differ from the mean of UNI. UAS factor variance does not differ from UNI variance.

^a According to earlier theory AUS3 WITH AUS9, AUS45 WITH AUS60, AUS45 WITH AUS27, AUS51 WITH AUS27

^b AUS9, AUS3, AUS45

^c AUS3

Table S.11*Measurement Invariance Tests of Ease of Participation (4 items)*

Model	χ^2	df	p	SC	RMSEA	CFI	TLI	SRMR	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δdf	p
M1	0.504	4	.973	1.3451	0	1.0	1.0	.006	NA	NA	NA
M2	5.901	7	.551	1.1951	0	1.0	1.0	.040	6.40	3	.093
M3	10.399	10	.406	1.1390	.012	.999	.999	.046	4.75	3	.191
M4	24.806	14	.037	1.2734	.052	.970	.974	.095	12.27	4	.015
M4mod ^a	18.759	13	.131	1.2636	.039	.984	.985	.073	7.06	3	.070

Note. UAS factor mean does not differ from UNI mean. Factor variance of UAS does not differ from UNI factor variance.

^a AUS14

Furthermore, systematic response style was investigated using unmeasured latent method factor technique (Podsakoff et al., 2012). The latent method factor was allowed to load to all items (loadings constrained to 1) but was uncorrelated with factors. The latent method factor slightly improved the original eight-factor model (RMSEA = .051, SRMR = .082, CFI = .92, TLI = .90). Most of the loadings to factors and all correlations between the factors decreased compared with the original model. All loadings to the method factor were significant ($p < .001$), ranging from .31 to .60.

The results indicated systematic method factor effect and, therefore, the possible presence of response style in the data additional to the final model with eight agency factors. Because significant method factor was confirmed, response style or internal dispositions may have directed the participants to answer the questionnaire, for example, in an extreme, mild, or socially desirable way (Bruzios & Harwood, 2020; Podsakoff, 2012), the source of significant method factor and response style should be investigated further with the AUS scale.

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